

The Ionisation Potential of Hydrogen Fluoride.

BY

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The ionisation potentials of hydrochloric, hydrobromic and hydriodic acids have been determined experimentally by Foote and Mohler (HCl only, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1832) and Franck and Knipping (*Zeit. Physik*, 1921, 7, 328). The experimental difficulties involved in a direct determination of the ionisation potential of hydrofluoric acid are obvious. It is therefore of some interest to calculate this value indirectly. Two attempts have so far been made in this direction. Turner (*Phil. Mag.*, 1924, 48, 1010), on the basis of a linear relationship which he found to exist between the atomic numbers and the quantum defects computed from the ionisation potentials of the hydrogen halide molecules, calculated the ionisation potential of HF to be 17.9 ± 0.5 volts. More recently Glockler (*Phil. Mag.*, 1925, 50, 997) has calculated this value from thermochemical considerations based on the value obtained by Grimm and Herzfeld (*Zeit. Physik*, 1923, 19, 141) for the difference between the heat of dissociation of the fluorine molecule (D_f) and the electron affinity (E_f) of the fluorine atom and finds it to be 15.67 ± 0.7 volts. Again, obtaining D_f and E_f by extrapolating the known values for the other halogens and obtaining an independent value for ($D_f - E_f$), the ionisation potential was found to come out to be 15 volts. The values obtained by these two

authors are very much higher than those for other hydrogen halides which lie close to one another.

HI	...	12.6 volts ¹
HBr	...	13.0 ,,
HCl	...	13.59 ,,

Glockler considers that a certain amount of uncertainty exists about the values of D_f and E_f which he used in his calculations. A value lower than that of Glockler has been obtained below from calculations made from a slightly different standpoint from that of Glockler, the thermochemical data made use of being of a more certain nature.

Fajans (*Ber. Deut. Phys. Ges.*, 1919, 21, 549) in extending the work of Börn on lattice energies pointed out that the heat of solution of a solid salt may be regarded as the sum of two effects, *viz.*, (1) the heat required to convert the solid salt into free gas ions, or what is the same as lattice energy and (2) the heat of solution of these gas ions.

Potassium fluoride and potassium chloride have the same lattice structure as rock salt. According to the calculations of Fajans and Herzfeld (*Zeit. Physik*, 1920, 2, 309) the lattice energies for potassium fluoride and chloride are 192.2 and 159.0 kilo. cal. respectively. The heats of solution of KF and KCl are +3.6 and -4.4 respectively (Landolt and Börnstein's *Tables*). Expressed in equation form—

¹ These values are taken from Franck (*Zeit. Physik*, 1922, 11, 160).

Adding

Similarly,

or,

Again

Adding

The solution of hydrofluoric acid is quite different from that of strong acids. Very little of HF is found to be ionised in solution and when its neutralisation is effected by strong alkalis, the amount of heat evolved is 2.6 k. cal. greater than in the case of the other halogen hydrides. Here if we assume that HF exists in solution practically as non-ionised, we can regard this excess of heat of neutralisation as the heat liberated in the process of the ionisation of the acid.

Guntz (*Compt. rend.*, 1883, 96, 1659) found the heat of solution of HF to be 11.8 k. cal.

and

Adding

$$\text{HF}_{\text{gas}} + \text{aq} = \overset{+}{\text{H}}_{\text{aq}} + \overset{-}{\text{F}}_{\text{aq}} + 14.4 \text{ k. cal.} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

If x be the ionisation energy of HF_{gas} in heat units,

$$\overset{+}{\text{H}}_{\text{gas}} + \overset{-}{\text{F}}_{\text{gas}} = \text{HF}_{\text{gas}} + x.$$

Combining this with equation (3), we get

$$\overset{+}{\text{H}}_{\text{gas}} + \overset{-}{\text{F}}_{\text{gas}} + \text{aq} = \overset{+}{\text{H}}_{\text{aq}} + \overset{-}{\text{F}}_{\text{aq}} + (14.4 + x). \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Now, subtracting (2) from (4), we have

$$(\overset{-}{\text{F}}_{\text{gas}} + \text{aq}) - (\overset{-}{\text{Cl}}_{\text{gas}} + \text{aq}) = \overset{-}{\text{F}}_{\text{aq}} - \overset{-}{\text{Cl}}_{\text{aq}} + x - 281.17 \dots \quad (5)$$

Equations (1) and (5) are identical. Thus we find

$$x - 281.17 - 41.2 = 0$$

or,

$$x = 622.87 \text{ k. cal.}$$

Expressed in volts

$$V_i (\text{the ionisation potential of HF}) = 14.02$$

The assumption made above that HF exists in solution practically as non-ionised is only approximately correct; so that this introduces a small error in the value of x we have arrived at. But this error would be very small when expressed in volts. It will be seen that the value obtained in this calculation is only 0.5 volts higher than the ionisation potential of HCl.

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